

DEVELOPING LEADERSHIP STYLES (TRANSFORMATIVE, CHARISMATIC & FUTURISTIC) AND GREEN ENTREPRENEURIAL ADVANTAGES AS MEDIATING TO LEVERAGE FIRM PERFORMANCE. CASES OF INDONESIA SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES

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Abstract

Current study tries to build relationship among transformative competency (TC), charismatic leadership skill (CLS) and futuristic leadership competency (FLC) on firm performance (OP) mediated by GEA. Current survey conducted to collect information from employees from manufactures and services as the unit analysis. Data gathering deployed two stages which covered the pilot study and survey analysis. Non-probability sampling as research method with convenience technique. Factor analysis, regression as well as other statistical were conducted. Exploratory factor analysis was also deployed for current study. The instrument of present study was developed through literature study on green entrepreneurial advantages, leadership style (charismatic, futuristic, and transformative) and firm performance. Common Method Bias (CMB) also conducted to avoid possible bias and external interference. Omitting bias by reviewing all variables from previous studies. Research finding demonstrated that all leadership styles showed the significant factor as the antecedents of firm performance. Moreover, the relationship also strengthened through GEA.

Keywords: Firm Growth, Green Entrepreneurship Advantages, Leadership Styles, Entrepreneurial Leadership.

1. INTRODUCTION

Environmental friendly and customer's consumption behaviour could leverage the level of firm environmental friendly that deployed green product or green process to reduce goods and services. Some previous studies have developed the relationship between green business practices on firm performance (Do et al., 2020, Baker and Sinkula, 2005, Ndubisi and Nair, 2009). Currently customers realized the need of sanitation and free from pollutant. Many people like to use organic food and services.

Due to the needs of good health and the confession of good environment, the total of green firm is increased all over the world. Green Entrepreneurship is a concept which aligned with green environmental approach and help to keep ecosystem balance, minimize pollution and waste, reduce gas emission and provide green products and services to increase the responsible consumption concept. Green Entrepreneurship is the typical of social entrepreneurship where the entrepreneurs are eager to promote the environment.

GE is the attempt to minimize the environment records such as environmental cost and social cost which derived from entrepreneurship activity (Fatoki, 2019). Besides, green business acted like catalisator for businessmen to contribute on higher social economics due to this business

to protect customers' health and society, create work opportunity and offer required green resources such as renewable energy, which lead to stimulate economic growth (ILO, 2012).

Entrepreneurship motivations have been explained at the level of organization (Miller, 1983, Stevenson and Jarillo, 1990) individual level (Mintzberg, 1973). This study, the author considered the entrepreneurship as the level of organization and then became the organizational growth. So, some organizational factors affected entrepreneurship activities and performance as well as organizational growth. Firm factors such as culture, structure, strategies, leadership, personality and entrepreneurship behavioural. Current research also considered different leadership styles and their relationship with entrepreneurial and organizational growth. Within entrepreneurial context, green entrepreneurial advantage is also discussed.

Research of (Ensley et al., 2006, Elenkov and Manev, 2005, Harrison and Roomi, 2018) considered different leadership as a basic organizational component which motivate entrepreneurial action. A few studies discussed the leadership relationship with green business (Gupta et al., 2004, Eyal and Kark, 2004, Coglisier and Brigham, 2004, Van Hemmen et al., 2013, Felix et al., 2019). Nevertheless, author considered the different leadership styles, in the context of green entrepreneurial. Meanwhile, green entrepreneurial advantage is the most important phenomenon from the various point of view, however there are still many factors are still remaining unsolved, mainly in the setting of different organizational variable such as leadership.

Some research materials which covered leadership styles LS (Yukl, 2012). In general, this study will look modern leadership as new leadership (it includes charismatic leadership skill and futuristic leadership competency) and also discuss the transformative competency. The leadership concept and green entrepreneurship advantages are dragged attention in many fields and later on considered as independent. Mostly GEA is a discussion in the field of social entrepreneurship. The form of leadership which is aligned with organizational behaviour sector as well as management focused on organizational development.

GEA in the field of social entrepreneurship emphasized on business creation or new organization. Though there were various studies have been conducted focused on the relationship among leadership styles and entrepreneurship, there are lack of research which specific exploration among leadership styles and entrepreneurship in the context of organization. There were gaps of understanding on how each leadership could affect the development of entrepreneurship advantages, especially in the quick shifting business environment

With some considerations described above, firstly, current study tries to build relationship among transformative competency (TC), charismatic leadership skill (CLS) and futuristic leadership competency (FLC) on organizational performance (OP) mediated by GEA. Secondly, evaluate and review previous studies related, with TC, CLS, FLC, GEA and OP, thirdly proposing hypotheses, fourthly research method. Fifth, finding and analysis. Discussion and conclusion at the sixth part. The last part of this study is limitation and further research.

2.1 Green Entrepreneurship Advantages (GEA)

The concept of entrepreneurship covered long history in the business field. The central theme of entrepreneurship developed the value creation which leads to innovation, creativity and problem solving (Drucker, 1985). This concept is recently applied in social problems and environment; this concept also has been through in the various implications. Some of them focused on green business produce green trading or basically categorized in green business with social impact, meanwhile, focused on social firm as society enhancement. GEA could be defined as new entity creation which engaged with the innovation and measurement (Thornton, 1999). Green could be meant as the responsibility on environment or delivering solution on problem solving on old cases with a better approach. The concept of GE is still considered new and drew attention since 1990s (Harini and Meenakshi, 2012).

GEA could make it business becomes green or just start up green business (OECD, 2010). In another hands, it could be defined as the business men worked on green zone, included the individual's trial on one category sustainability with green environmental innovation (design, process, as well as ecological product services) which reduces resources or increase efficiency on waste reduction (Gunawan and Fraser, 2016). Green business referred on a product character, renewable and ecological policy in an organization (Lotfi et al., 2018). Besides, there are two kind of business, firstly the one produced green product and deployed green technical in product lines (Fatoki, 2019)

Similar with the aforementioned statements, in accordance with (ILO, 2012), green business could be characterized from the two point of view related with the output (Product and Services) and process (raise). There are some terminologies closely related with GE, such as environment entrepreneurial, sustainable entrepreneurial (Spence et al., 2011, Kushwaha and Sharma, 2017). Sometimes, these type of entrepreneurship is somehow considered as social entrepreneurship as it considered as innovative, the activities in social value creation which is possible happen in or among non-profit sectors, commercial or government. Besides, it provides the platform for innovation and job opportunity creation, solving unemployment problem and uncondisive environment.

Entrepreneurs are businessmen who think new business plan and start with risk taking and change the ideas to become real business. A green entrepreneur as businessmen with green business utilization goals. The success of green business is generally depend on the nature of entrepreneurship itself, business idea, and firm infrastructures environmental. The concept of GE is more related with the sustainability and applied in various industries, this also promoted the environment sustainability.

Positive nature from green entrepreneurship is crucial for or organization performance and its development. As a part of entrepreneurship, GE also has quality to higher risk taking, innovator, which motivates higher intrinsics. Green business required green bases to become superior and increase performance. Green infrastructures is firm environment which consist of organizational structures, organizational culture, and control mechanism. To widen this type of environment, an entrepreneur should build the culture where individual should claimed the

environment upgrading as economics prospect and competitive, not as a cost or threat. Besides, green infrastrucutu should be flrsible, until it covers and fulfill shifting environmental needs. GE has ea significant relationship with sustainable performance in various industries, such as tourism, hotel, agriculture, construction and renewable energy industries.

GE could play crucial role in overcome the social challenges, economics and current environment, and commitment to goal achievement. The attempt of green business as the other types of business is to environmental maintenance. Defining green business is not just the simple trading, but as social action which direct on security and environment protection (Lotfi et al., 2018).

2.2. Leadership Style

The leadership played the dominan role in acieving the strategic plans, a fundamental basis for the organizational succees (Kumar et al., 2017, Kumar and Kaptan, 2007). The concept of leadership has been existed in the field of business. Considering the entrepreneurship, the relationship between leadership and the focus of entrepreneurship offered constructive contribution on the organization success. Stating that if the vital and efficient leadership is not existed, it eill lead to the difficulties for individual to maintain their productivity, efficiency and competitive advantages (Lussier and Achua, 2007). This is also as the main triggering to increase business performance.

Leadership could be defined in many ways related with the individual level or organization in the sector of business and management. It also claimed as behaviour or process or actions or the way to persuade others. In another way, the leadership is the process to engage all employess in doing the tasks or goals and affected the behaviour or activities of others. In addition, it is a process of social interaction between individuals (Muralidharan and Pathak, 2019). Current studywas based on common leadership theory which is centered on leadership behaviour on employee in many working situations. This theory contributed on study concerned on the leadership topic through the characteristic and nature of leadership. In additional, this study, leadership is designed in many behaviours such as TC, CLS and FLC.

Moreover, this study foused on the LS in the level of organization since there were many findings claimed that LS is a significant predictor from organizational performance, and the important variable which affects the function of organizational member (Wu, 2009, Bass et al., 2003, Yahaya and Ebrahim, 2016). Defining the LS as the interesting concept during the last decades (Burns, 1978). He also defined transformative skill as the supportive relationship and motivate followers became leaders and leaders turn to agen of morales. At the same time, charismatic leadership has the intereting aspect as it has been developed within leadership study during the last decades (Yukl, 2012). Leaderhip with charismatic skill insire many people or goup to work better and do the best for better entity or wider society. During the crisis, charismatic leadership happnd due to the core faith, institution, and organizational credibility (Takala, 2004).

Business leadership provided extra care to create vision and searched for the changes to make sure firm long term growth (Kumar et al., 2021, Bass, 1999, Jha et al., 2020, Rowe, 2001).

Entrepreneurship is the multifacet phenomenon which engaged some action for innovation, imagination, proactive, opportunity exploration, business creation and risk taking in technology and product development (Eyal and Kark, 2004, Shane, 2004).

3. HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT AND RESEARCH MODEL

3.1. Hypoteses Development

3.1.1. Relationship between Leadership Styles (LS) and Green Entrepreneurship Advantageous. (GEA)

Eventhough the leadership and entrepreneurship are different phenomenon and considered unique in management, there were double conseptuals existed between them. Currently, leadership is claimed as mature field, and the entrepreneurship is relatively new. The concept of leadership had been existed since very long time ago, with quality, behaviour, explored leadership procedures from vaious ancient sources, Italy, Egypt, Israel, Greek, India and China (Cogliser and Brigham, 2004). There are leadership attributes and entrepreneurship shared such as planning, vision and impact. Moreover, they were not exactly shared the same characters, but there are some similarities, like the concept of impact, vision, planning and progress (Fernald et al., 2005). The most general leadership interpretation easily noticed such as the power to influence people to achieve goals. Besides, leadership is the process that demanded all employees to conduct the task and goals as well as to persuade their behaviour and action on others (Kumar and Sharma, 2018).

The leadership could also be defined as the different perspectives, such as behaviour approach, contingency approach as well as charismatics and attitude approaches. Leadership and entrepreneurship also categorized in the nature and behaviour approach, due to the entrepreneurship emphasized not only in the entrepreneur but also on the various types of entrepreneur with lucrative choices (Shane and Venkataraman, 2001); and leadership focused on the capacity to influence others toward goals and found innovative ways to implement the programs in organization. Some people also shared ideas that entrepreneurship could be as uncommon leadership (Vecchio, 2003) and furhtermore, (Venkataraman, 1997) defined as the discovery, evaluation and exploitative potential choice which produced future product and services. In another hands, the leadership is viewed as the creation process through social intuition among people (Fairhurst and Uhl-Bien, 2012).

In accordance of aboved definition, GRA and Leadership are interconnected. (Conger et al., 2000) described the charismatic leadership had entrepreneurial mind set and change natural driven. Besides, the type of leadership emphasized on changes and organizational development (Howell and Higgins, 1990). GEA required different characteristics such as changes, innovation and proactive approach. The consistent entrepreneurshial also itself such as teamoriented, transformational and charismatic, humanistic-oriented as well as paticipative leadership competency (Felix et al., 2019, Muralidharan and Pathak, 2019, Eyal and Kark, 2004, Stephan and Pathak, 2016).

3.1.1.1. Relationship between Transformative Competency and GEA and FP

GEA and its development has been rapidly increased for the last decade. As the consequences, the sustainability and performance or firm growth has important aspect. Many organizational variables played important roles in entrepreneurial development or organizational development, such as organizational cultural, structural, strategic and leadership. Some of them are, leadership variable was considered as the important factors on organizational growth. Some previous studies showed the strong relationship and constructive between leadership and entrepreneurship (Howell and Avolio, 1993).

Transformative leadership competency has been identified as the most learned from the leadership theories within 20 years and affected in many traits (Simola et al., 2010, Judge and Piccolo, 2004). This leadership is a method triggering the care on firm goals and empower the followers to achieve the goals (Stone et al., 2004). Leadership itself categorized within for traits, such as idealized control, motivated inspiring, intellectual stimulatory and personalized cares (Bass and Riggio, 2006, Bass, 1999), each of this traits could be used to affect the environment sustainability in organization.

Green entrepreneurs kept on trying to produce creative ideas or innovative as well as changes. This is such a good work to ensure and educate society to protect and safe environment. Moreover, green entrepreneurship used the opportunities and introduce business to sustain development which contributed on structural transformation, socially dedicated and technologically moved forward which based on the environmentally friendly (Walley and Taylor, 2002). Besides, the orientation of GEA is possible to identify business opportunity with environmental aspect consideration (Ge et al., 2018). As the consequences, the leadership trait affected GRA.

Furthermore, transformative leadership is the most suitable in GEA (Eyal and Kark, 2004, Stephan and Pathak, 2016) and leverage the motivation to use environmental product and services. This is increased the satisfaction, commitment, loyalty and followers' expenditures. Based on the aforementioned findings, this is to propose the following hypothesis.

H1. Transformative Competency leadership has a significant impact on GEA.

H1a: Transformative Competency leadership has a significant impact on FP

3.1.1.3. Relationship between Charismatic Leadership Skill and GEA and FP

Conger et al. (2000) claimed that the role of CLS showed the impacts during the leadership which supported by altruistic motivation. CLS and the transformative leadership are constantly used in turn due to the inspiration, motivation and influence. (Felix et al., 2019) CLS will inspired the increase of effort through creativity, vision, support and the deeper definition, which related with firm success, growth, proactive and skill of team decision making. CLS also has the beneficial impact on product creation and entrepreneurship (Chen et al., 2014, Muralidharan and Pathak, 2019). There is also relationship between CLS and innovation (Jung et al., 2003).

The innovation is considered as the basic aspect of GE. GE was created to contribute on people by adopting innovative process and harmless product on environment or business (Haldar, 2019). By managing GE, this type of leadership brought the modern environment which produced new business and supported by creativity, innovation and perception (Bass and Bass, 2008). Entrepreneurs need huge motivation to handle and sustain green business development.

Besides, entrepreneur should own the power to persuade others to consume environmental products and services. The nature of CLS motivated scholars to increase the capability and achieve goals and growth (Felix et al., 2019). This could help to build interesting visions for experts to achieve higher result related with innovation (Burns, 1978). In accordance (Shamir et al., 1993, Van Knippenberg et al., 2004), CLS affected the strong team growth. Aligning with the previous consideration, current research proposed the hypotheses, as follows:

H2. The higher CLS brings the significant impact on GEA.

H2a. The higher CLS brings the significant impact on fP.

3.1.1.4. Relationship between Futuristic Leadership Competency (FLC) with Green Entrepreneurial Advantages

At the very beginning, FL described as the process of three steps such as empowerment (Act), communication (word) and vision (ideas) (Westley and Mintzberg, 1989). These were characterized as competency to form and describe clear vision and delivered values for organizational performance (Taylor et al., 2014, Nanus, 1992, Sashkin, 1992). This emphasized of opportunities creation and new possibility, empower the relationship as well as creative creative and innovative action.

Various authors defined FLC as leader who emphasized on the vision or futuristics were more success are well-known as visioner or futuristic leadership and claimed as the best choice in organization (Çınar and Kaban, 2012). In many cases, this type of skill has a potency to achieve faster goal and also coordinated with business activities and also offered opportunities to develop organization capability (Breevaart et al., 2014, Taylor et al., 2014).

FLC was known with trust, a pro-social trait and organizational capability or skill (Sashkin dan Sashkin, 2002). Previous findings showed that futuristic leadership took responsibilities over firm's significant growth (Taylor et al., 2014, Nanus, 1992). Furthermore, FLC offered the collaboration, inspiration, participation, trust and high efficiency in new organization. Based on the above discussion, this is to propose the following hypothesis:

H3. The higher Futuristic Leadership Competency (FLC), the significant impact on GEA

H3A. The higher Futuristic Leadership Competency (FLC), the significant impact on FP

3.1.2. Relationship between GEA and Firm Performance.

It is such a big challenge to define organization growth or performance due to the multi-facet phenomenon (Delmar et al., 2003). In accordance with (Nelson and Winter, 1982), firms' growth was derived from organization capital integration competencies and procedures. In another hands, growth definition as firms' earnings and assets (Penrose, 2009).

Growth defined as the organizational measurement changes when it measured with workfoces measurement or organization works and the development itself defined as organization ages change. Organization performance is all about differences in various organizations. An organization could select many parameters to measure its growth.

Organization, in general, currently operate with advance technology in dynamic global environment. The volatility, uncertainty, challenges and competition, insufficient resources and needs for continues improvement led to entrepreneurship to become the most crucial sources for sustainability, development and organizational efficiency (Howell and Avolio, 1993, Damanpour, 1991).

Aligning with (Miller, 1983), the direction of entrepreneurship regarding on investment in product innovation, strategic traits, and risk taking. As result, it is known as high correlation intention with growth (Wiklund and Shepherd, 2005, Covin and Slevin, 1989, Moreno and Casillas, 2008).

Menurut (Hillman, 1994), growth is organization evaluation rocess with continues maturity to observe what was done and what will be doing, while the creativity itself is a bases for organizational growth. This is to propose the following hypothesis.

H4. The higher level of GEA brings the significant impact on Organizational Performance.

For more briefly, proposed model is illustrated as follows.

Fig.1: Grand Theoretical Model

Source: Literature Reviw (2023)

The following table described the reseach variable, indicators and variable definitions. (See table)

Table 1: Research Variables, Indicators and Definition

Variables	Indicators	Definition
Transformative Competency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capability to create new value. • Capability to reconcile tension and dilemmas • Having soft skill, teamwork, initiative, & planning • Ability to meet complex demand • Ability to mobilize psychosocial resources 	The type of leadership with capabilities to create new value, reconsil tension and dilemmas, embedded with soft skill, teamwork, initiative, planning, as well as ability to meet complex demand and mobilize psychological resources.
Charismatic Leadership Skill	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having coaching ability to navigate teams & future changes • Specialized areas of expertise to direct organization. • Ability on work collaboration & consulting role. • Green Public procurement • Participatory oriented Planning 	CLS is defined as the ability to coach and navigate teams and future changes, the expertise to direct organization, collaboration and conculc role, ability to adapt with green public procurement and the willingness to participate oriented planning
Futuristic Leadership Competency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A competency to learn the past and execute for future. • A competence to visualize brand new ideas and opinion • A capability to think further and apply timely • A capability to forecast changes for competition. 	FLC could be defined as a competency to learn the past and execute for future, ability to visualize brand new ideas and opinion, skill to think further and apply timely and forecast future changes for competition.
Green Entrepreneurship Advantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The advantages of green practices which delivered social and environmental issues. • The advantages that offered benefits to reduce pollution, restore ecosystem, efficiency. • Advantages through enduring the commitmen on resources • The advantages gained from the improvement employees as resources 	GEA is defined as the advantages of firm gained from green practices such as pollution reduction, restore ecosystem, efficiency, enduring the commitment on resources as well as the improvement of employess as resources.
Organizational Performance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broading the market performance • High level of organization Financial • High level of shareholder value • High respond on through effective decision-making • High dissemination within CSR 	OP defined as the high performance obtained by firms with market performance, level of financial, shareholder value, effective decision making and organization dissemination through CSR.

Source: Literatures reviewed (2022)

Variable Measurement

A ten Likert scale was used to measure the respondent’s choice where 1 is for strongly disagree and 10 addressing strongly agree.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + e$$

Where;

β_0 - Constant

Y- Dependent variable (Organization Performance-OP)

X1= Independent variable (Transformative Competency - TC)

X2= Independent variable (Charismatic Leadership Skill - CLS)

X3= Independent variable (Futuristic Leadership Competency - FLC)

X4= Independent variable – Moderating (Green Entrepreneurship Advantages - GEA)

$\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = Regression coefficient for each exogenous

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 Conceptual Description and Sampling

Current survey conducted to collect information from employees from manufactures and services as the unit analysis. Data gathering deployed two stages which covered the pilot study and survey analysis. Non-probability sampling as research method with convenience technique. Factor analysis, regression as well as other statistical were conducted. Exploratory factor analysis was also deployed for current study. 400 questionnaires were distributed and 360 are valid for further analysis. Current survey is completed in the level if managerial and executives as the target of population. Table 2 illustrated the demographic of respondents.

Table 2: Summation of Respondents Demographic

Profile	Classification	Frequency	(%)
Respondents	• Male	236	65,55
	• Female	124	34,45
	Total	360	100
Background	• Manufacturing industries	149	41,39
	• Service organization	120	33,33
	• Other	91	25,28
	Total	360	
Age	• 20–24 ears	2	0,05
	• 25–29 years	15	4,47
	• 30–34 years	56	15,57
	• 35–40 years	67	18,61
	• Above 40 years	220	61,11
	Total	360	
Industry classification	• Business services	16	4,44
	• Agricultural products	52	14,44
	• Marketing Textile	45	12,5
	• FMCG	12	3,33
	• Energy and power	8	2,22
	Total	100	27,78

Profile	Classification	Frequency	(%)
	• Health and medical	30	8,33
	• Retailing	97	26,94
	• Other		
	Total	360	
Position in the organization	• CEO/Founder	23	6,38
	• Senior executive	68	18,89
	• Manager Board Member Consultant	120	33,33
	• Human resource (HR)	117	32,5
	• Other	32	8,89
	Total	360	
Number of employees	• 1–20	4	1,11
	• 21–50	25	6,94
	• 51–100 More	87	24,17
	• than 100	244	67,78
	Total	360	

Source: Developed by Authors (2023)

4.2 Measurement and Survey Tools

The instrument of present study was developed through literature study on Green entrepreneurship advantages, leadership style (charismatic (5 items), futuristic (4 items), and transformative (5 items) and organization performance (5 items). For more detail, see the following table 3.

4.3 Data Preparation

Current study conduct 3 different step in data preparation. Firstly: choosing question. Some question in the survey instrument are taken from the previous studies. Some questions are proposed such as green marketing, green product, opportunity in green investment, environmental friendly and avoiding hazardous acts which relevant to measure GEA. (Kumar and Sharma, 2018, de Hoogh et al., 2004, Conger and Kanungo, 1998, Khatri et al., 2001); and analyze the content of literatures based on GRA and leadership and validated by statistical tools. Secondly: examining the outliers. The outliers and data normalization is verified. For the type of leadership, it did not find any extreme outliers as well as GRA and OP. Thirdly, Partial Respond Checking. In this steps, processing the incomplete data. For 360 questionnaires are valid for further analysis.

4.4. Common Method Bias (CMB)

CMB also conducted to avoid possible bias and external interference. Omitting bias by reviewing all variables from previous studies.

4.5 Testing the Reliability and Validity

Analyzing the reliability showed how well all the indicators correlated one another. Internal reliability analyzed through Cronbach alpha (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). Alpha Cronbach (α) should exceed 0,7 to indicate the questionnaires are reliable (Nunnally, 1978, Cuieford, 1965,

Kumar et al., 2017). Analysis reliability and principal component factor for all indicators. Exploratory Factor Analysis was conducted to reduce and analyze data (Hair et al., 2006). Moreover, convergen validity, higher loading factor from 0,5(Field, 2009).

Table 4: Scale Accuracy Analysis (SAA)

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), Summary of Measurement Scale Results, Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and Validity

Dimensions	Indicators	Standardized Loading (λ)	AV E	Alpha (α)	CR
Transformative Competency	• Capability to create new value.	0.75	0,71,	0,74	0,76
	• Capability to reconcile tension and dilemmas	0.71			
	• Having soft skill, teamwork, initiative, & planning	0.76			
	• Ability to meet complex demand	0.69			
	• Ability to mobilize psychosocial resources	0.66			
Charismatic Leadership Skill	• Having coaching ability to navigate teams & future changes	0.85	0,74	0,76	0,78
	• Specialized areas of expertise to direct organization.	0.84			
	• Ability on work collaboration & consulting role.	0.68			
	• Green Public procurement	0.69			
	• Participatory oriented Planning	0.67			
Futuristic Leadership Competency	• A competency to learn the past and execute for future.	0.79	0,68	0,70	0,72
	• A competence to visualize brand new ideas and opinion	0.60			
	• A capability to think further and apply timely	0.71			
	• A capability to forecast changes for competition	0.65			
Green Entrepreneurship Advantages	• The advantages of green practices which delivered social and environmental issues.	0.73	0,76	0,78	0,80
	• The advantages that offered benefits to reduce pollution, restore ecosystem, efficiency.	0.79			
	• Advantages through enduring the commitment on resources	0.79			
	• The advantages gained from the improvement employees as resources	0.76			
Organizational Performance	• Broaden the market performance	0.58	0,70	0,72	0,74
	• High level of organization Financial	0.64			
	• High level of shareholder value	0.76			
	• High respond on through effective decision-making	0.83			
	• High dissemination within CSR	0.69			

Source(s): Statistical Output (2023)

Table 4: Discriminant validity

Construct	1	2	3	4	5
Transformative Competency	0,86				
Charismatic Leadership Skill		0,82			
Futuristic Leadership Competency			0,84		
Green Entrepreneurship Advantages				0,80	
Organizational Performance					0,81

Source(s): Statistical Output (2023)

Table 5: Discriminant Validity (the HTMT ratio)

Construct	1	2	3	4	5
Transformative Competency	0,67				
Charismatic Leadership Skill	0,73	0,86			
Futuristic Leadership Competency	0,66	0,77	0,87		
Green Entrepreneurship Advantages	0,74	0,79	0,83	0,78	
Organizational Performance	0,68	0,76	0,82	0,84	0,83

Source(s): Statistical Output (2023)

Evaluation of Full Structural Model

Proposing direct relationship, mediating and indirect relationship. Transformative Competency, Charismatic Leadership Skill and Futuristic Leadership Skill (Endogen), and Green Entrepreneurship Advantages as mediating, finally Organizational Performance (Exogenous). For more details, see fig. 2.

Fig 2: Full Structural Model

Source: Statistical output of SEM with AMOS (2023)

Data analysis conducted in accordingly based on 360 valid questionnaires to investigate the direct and indirect relationship among hypotheses. All the proposed hypotheses showed the significant impact as the antecedents of organizational performance. Besides, a good model was analyzed from the measurement and model categories. Current model described from three aspects such as the absolute, incremental as well as parsimony. The criterias of model showed that Chi-Square = 336,7 df=220 P=0,000 Cm/DF= 1,53, GFI=0,953, AGFI=0,913, TLI= 0,964, CFI=0,969, NFI= 0,915 dan RMSEA = 0,037 dan Hoelter (348). Having met all the requirements current research model claimed fit

Hypothesis Testing and Regression Weights

Transformative Competencies owned by leaders showing a significant impact GEA as H1 is accepted (CR 2,91). Transformative characters are proven to increase green entrepreneurial. This is to strongly suggest to sustain and maintain transformative traits among leader. It also has a significant impact on organizational performance as H1a accepted (CR 2,68). Secondly, the charismatic trait as a leadership skill played crucial impact on GEA (CR 2,91) and H2 is accepted. Meanwhile it also showed the significant impact on organizational performance (CR 2,44) AS H2a is also accepted. Charismatic competencies are strongly to sustain and maintain among leadership in orde to increase performance as well as green entrepreneurship. Thirdly, the is a strong relationship between futuristic leadership on GEA as H3 is accepted (CR 2,96) and it has significant impact on OP (CR 4,46) as H3a is also received. Lastly, the strong relationship and significant impact of GEA on OP (CR 4,30) as H4 is accepted. To maintain and sustain high level of organization performance, firms should apply and deploy green entrepreneurial aspect in running organization or firms. For more details, see table. 3

**Table 3: Regression Weights
Hypotheses Testing**

Hypotheses			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Green Entrepreneurship Advantages	<---	Charismatic Leadership Skill	,222	,076	2,913	,004
Green Entrepreneurship Advantages	<---	Transformative Competency	,240	,082	2,936	,003
Green Entrepreneurship Advantages	<---	Futuristic Leadership Competency	,335	,113	2,962	,003
Organizational Performance	<---	Green Entrepreneurship Advantages	,230	,054	4,300	***
Organizational Performance	<---	Futuristic Leadership Competency	,427	,096	4,461	***
Organizational Performance	<---	Charismatic Leadership Skill	,148	,061	2,443	,015
Organizational Performance	<---	Transformative Competency	,175	,065	2,680	,007

Source: statistical output of SEM with AMOS (2022)

5. DISCUSSION

This study is expected to deepen and widen our understanding and knowledge among leadership traits on green entrepreneurial advantages. It is strongly suggested to analyze the integrated frameworks when leadership traits such charismatic, transformative and futuristic has a direct relationship on GEA and organization performance. As many as four hypotheses were explained the leadership traits are fully claimed as the antecedents of GEA as well as OP. Charismatic leadership skill is shown a significant impact on GEA as well as on OP (Chen et al., 2014, Muralidharan and Pathak, 2019).

Previous study showed that there was not any relationship between GEA and Charismatic leadership styles. Knowing the many factors of charismatic traits such as proactive, innovative and also team decision making skill affected the innovation and GEA. This finding also confirmed the previous study (Burns, 1978).

There are robust studies proven the futuristics leadership skill had a significant impact on GEA. Motivating employess to help achieving firms goal and mission by sharing team image and firms' future (Luo et al., 2020). (Westley and Mintzberg, 1989) claimed that futuristic was not only relevan to motivate and mobilize the supporters to achieve firms' goals in the future but also relevan with strategic process. Besides, futuristic leadership skill is also related with organization performance and the spirit of innovation. The futuristic leaders are also the initiator of changes management. (Bass, 1985, Hater and Bass, 1988) highlighted the positive relationship with employees' perception about effective leadership and employees' satisfaction. As concequence, current research could claim that the futuristic leader has a significant impact on organization performance mediated by green entrepreneurial.

Current finding also highlighted the impact of GEA on organization performance. This finding is aligned with previous studies (Karlsson and Acs, 2002, Wiklund and Shepherd, 2005). Entrepreneurship orientation directed the organization toward new market opportunities (Engelen et al., 2015). GEA has a strong impact on product differentiation and increase organization performance by leveraging the profitability, transparency risk management as well as earning growth (Demirel and Danisman, 2019). Entrepreneurial orientation could be engaged in product innovation, risk taking as well as proactive. GEA with innovation and new product creativity has huge capability to offer working field and new opportunities. The innovation itself is also considered as new capability to create risch resources.

6. RESEARCH IMPLICATION AND CONCLUSION

GEA is more important phenomenon from the many point of views, yet there are still many aspects left remain. This study contributed on green entrepreneurial, leadership traits as well as organization performance. Firstly, widen the discussion on green entrepreneurial in firm and explored the leadership from many perspectives which is mostly related with green entrepreneurial. These findings showed that the future of green business is promising due to the active roles in the growth and organization performance. Moreover, leadership traits have been identified as one of the most important individual determinant on firm innovation.

Aligning with it, leadership traits also played a crucial role in organization growth such as transformative leadership competence which could motivate the radical entrepreneurial in organization and support the creativity, innovation and the member of team research as well development. Futuristic leadership skill also has a positive and effective relationship on organization performance. Charismatic leadership motivated the followers to achieve and pursue higher target and goals. This study was conducted in accordance with robust literatures. In this study, the relationship of leadership traits was empirically analyzed with GEA and OP. though most recently, various studies on GE. This study expanded the literatures on GE by emphasizing on the importance of leadership who promoted the new business development. From the management point of view, these findings contributed in understanding the main sources of GEA and leadership traits on OP.

Current research limitation offered the additional opportunities to deeper research. The limitation included the sample measurement and its method. For respondent access, a non-probability sampling technique (targeted and snowball sampling) was deployed which triggered the representative cases in related with all population and narrowing the finding generalization (Spren and Zwaagstra, 1994).

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